

PEDAGOGICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL MECHANISMS FOR THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL CONTENT AND A VIRTUAL PLATFORM IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

This article analyzes the theoretical and basic aspects of the technology for creating national educational content and a virtual educational platform in a digital educational environment. In the context of the digital transformation of the modern education system, the need for virtual platforms that take into account national content and language characteristics is increasing. The article covers existing foreign experiences, platform architecture, content creation technologies and issues of their implementation in practice. As a result of the research, effective mechanisms for integrating national educational content into a digital platform, including the possibility of creating a virtual environment for special laboratories and practical exercises based on WordPress technology, are substantiated.

Keywords

digital education, virtual educational platform, national educational content, digital transformation, pedagogical technologies, educational platform architecture.

The rapid development of the digital economy and information and communication technologies requires a radical transformation of the education system. Today, the use of digital technologies at all stages of education, the creation of virtual learning environments, and the digitization of national educational content have become one of the urgent tasks. The reforms being implemented in the education sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan also identify the formation of a digital learning environment, the creation of national content and virtual platforms as a priority.

Virtual educational platforms eliminate the spatial and temporal limitations of traditional education and allow for the introduction of interactive, personalized and

flexible forms of learning. However, existing foreign platforms are often not adapted to the local language, mentality and curriculum, which creates the need to create national content and develop virtual platforms with national language resources.

The purpose of this study is to develop theoretical foundations, architectural solutions and practical implementation mechanisms for the technology of creating national educational content and a virtual educational platform in a digital educational environment.

Theoretical foundations of digital educational environments and virtual platforms. A digital educational environment is an integrated system that provides interaction between all participants in the educational process (teachers, students, administration) using information and communication technologies. Such an environment creates new opportunities for organizing, monitoring and evaluating the educational process.

A virtual educational platform is the technological basis of a digital educational environment and performs the following functions:

1. Storage and systematization of educational content;
2. Interactive communication between teachers and students;
3. Control and assessment of knowledge;
4. Management and analysis of the educational process.

International experience shows that effective virtual platforms should have an open architecture, modular structure and flexible interface. For example, a virtual platform created for teaching English in higher education in China demonstrates a systematic approach to content, methods, functions, importance and stages.

National educational content is the basis of digital transformation. National educational content is understood as a set of digital educational resources adapted to the requirements of the education system of a particular country or region, national language characteristics, cultural values and curricula.

When creating national content, it is necessary to adhere to the following basic requirements:

- Language compatibility: Content should be presented in Uzbek (in Latin script) and other necessary languages;

- Compliance with curricula: Compliance with national educational standards and curricula;

- Interactivity: The presence of elements that ensure the active participation of students (tests, simulations, tasks);

- Multimedia: A harmonious combination of text, audio, video, graphics, and animation elements.

Virtual learning platform architecture. Based on scientific literature and practical experience, the optimal architecture of a virtual learning platform should include the following components:

Technological layer

- Web server and database;
- Content management system (e.g. WordPress, Moodle);
- Multimedia resource storage and transcoding system.

Functional layer

- Content module: Systematization, categorization and search of educational materials;

- Communication module: Forums, chats, webinars and video conferencing tools;

- Control module: Tests, assignments, assessment system and reports;

- Management module: User registration, group management and statistics.

Interface layer

- Responsive (adaptive) design;

- Intuitive and convenient navigation;

- Visual elements reflecting the characteristics of the national language and culture.

Platform creation technology. When creating a national virtual educational platform, it is advisable to carry out the following technological stages:

Choosing a technological basis - Experience shows that open source systems (Moodle, WordPress) are effective due to their low cost, flexibility and wide support. Platforms created on the basis of WordPress allow you to organize interactive laboratory exercises using additional plugins.

Digitization and preparation of content - Scanning existing educational materials

and converting them into text format via OCR (optical character recognition); Creating video tutorials and animations; Developing interactive tests and assignments.

Configuring and customizing the platform

- Support for the national language (Latin script) and fonts;
- Creating a structure suitable for local curricula;
- Enriching the user interface with national design elements.

Testing and implementation

- Approving the platform in the real educational process;
- Collecting and analyzing user feedback;
- Elimination and improvement of shortcomings.

Results and discussion. The results of the study allow us to draw the following conclusions:

1. The importance of national content: Content that is appropriate for the national language and culture plays a significant role in improving the quality of education. Simply translating foreign platforms and content is not enough, but an approach that takes into account the specifics of the national education system is necessary.

2. Unity of technology and pedagogy: The effectiveness of a virtual platform is determined not only by a technological solution, but also by its combination with pedagogical methodology. When creating national content, modern pedagogical technologies (problem-based learning, project method, collaborative learning) should be taken into account.

3. The priority of open technologies: Open source platforms such as WordPress, Moodle are an economically and technologically effective tool for creating a virtual educational environment with national content.

4. Interactivity and flexibility: The platform should be adaptable to the level of knowledge and individual characteristics of students, as well as enriched with interactive elements (video, test, simulation).

Conclusion. Creating a national educational content and virtual educational platform in a digital educational environment is one of the important directions of digital transformation of the education system. This study developed the theoretical

foundations, architecture and practical implementation mechanisms of the platform creation technology.

When creating a national virtual platform, it is recommended to adhere to the following principles:

- reflect the characteristics of the national language and culture;
- use open and flexible technological solutions;
- ensure the harmony of pedagogical methodology and technology;
- create interactive and personalized learning opportunities.

In the future, it is advisable to continue research in the direction of developing the intellectual components of the platform (artificial intelligence, adaptive learning systems), as well as expanding national content for various disciplines and stages of education.

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